

CFD Analysis of Hypersonic Flow over a Spacecraft During Re-entry

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Abstract—Atmospheric re-entry is the movement of a body from space into and through the gases of an atmosphere of a planet. Re-entry capsules or control modules of a spacecraft are blunt bodies with heat shields which return after conducting spaceflight. The following paper showcases external flow analysis on the Apollo 11 re-entry vehicle, Columbia using computational fluid dynamics. The temperature variation, velocity profile, coefficients of lift and drag, and pressure distribution at the blunt end of the capsule are evaluated. The results of the simulation were discussed using velocity, temperature, and pressure contours.

Keywords— *Atmospheric Re-Entry, Hypersonic Flow, CFD, Temperature Distribution, Velocity Profile, Pressure Distribution, Lift and Drag Coefficients, Apollo 11*

1.

INTRODUCTION

During atmospheric re-entry, a spacecraft experiences extreme aerodynamic loads and thermal effects as it transitions from vacuum of space into the atmospheric environment of a planet. The re-entry process has complex fluid dynamics, where hypersonic flow conditions generate intense heating that can reach tens of thousands of degrees Kelvin. Re-entry capsules, such as the Apollo command modules, are specifically designed with a blunt-nose design, and is equipped with a heat shield or ablative Thermal Protection Systems (TPS) as well; [1] [1] which serves an aerodynamic purpose by creating a strong bow shock wave ahead of the capsule which decelerates the hypersonic flow, and helps avoid any potential damage of the capsule and insulate the vehicle body.

CFD simulations help in prediction of important parameters that would be rather complicated, and costly to conduct manually; to be able to simulate hypersonic flows computationally allows for comprehensive analysis of temperature variations, velocity profiles, and pressure distributions around re-entry vehicles, providing essential data for thermal protection system design and structural integrity assessment.

1.1. Aerodynamic Heating

Aerodynamic heating is the kinetic into thermal energy conversion due to the motion between a vehicle and fluid. This heating occurs due to either compression of the fluid at stagnation points, and friction along the surface of the

boundary layer where shear forces reduce motion between fluid particles and the vehicle skin. [2]

As velocity increases, heating intensifies dramatically, and these high temperatures can affect mechanical load distribution, weaken structural members requiring more weight, and generate thermal stresses that cause mechanical stress patterns due to differential material expansion rates. Atmospheric re-entry vehicles particularly experience severe aerodynamic heating during return. The velocities often exceed 25,000 feet (about 7.62 km) per second for orbital missions, consequently causing intense heating of all external surfaces. Stagnation regions, particularly at blunt-body sections, showcase the most severe conditions due to direct hypersonic flow impact and compression.

Thermal Protection Systems (TPS) integrated into heat shields are crucial for protecting structures from elevated heat on external surfaces. The fundamental design requires that energy released through aerodynamic heating must be effectively absorbed, dissipated, or rejected by the TPS. Modern heat shields employ various technologies including ablative materials that sacrifice themselves through charring or mass loss, refractory materials providing thermal resistance, and radiative cooling systems. [1] The Apollo command module's ablative heat shield, utilizing a honeycomb structure filled with ablative resin, expressing effective TPS selection for managing intense heating during high-velocity atmospheric re-entry.

2.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The reviewed papers employ various CFD approaches to simulate hypersonic flows over re-entry capsules. Shafeeque (2017) conducted CFD analysis on the Apollo AS-202 module using two softwares; first meshing in HYPERMESH and then analyzing in Ansys FLUENT with Spalart-Allmaras turbulence modeling, exhibiting the model's effectiveness for hypersonic applications due to its numerical robustness. The study incorporated extensive validation efforts using actual AS-202 flight data for comparison purposes and analyzed flow over the capsule at three varying Mach numbers and altitudes; revealing complex wake structures, particularly at non-zero angles of attack, where flow separation patterns varied significantly. The research reviewed the heat flux, pressure, temperature and velocity profile variations and also discussed direct

implications for thermal protection system design and material selection. [1]

Uppu et al. (2012) used a CFD code and numerically analyzed on 2D & 3D bodies for different flow regimes and geometries to understand the flow behavior over reentry capsules, namely EXPERT, OREX and FIRE II re-entry capsules; with a full Navier-Stokes solver to analyze flare-shaped re-entry vehicles at Mach numbers ranging from 6 to 15. Their work highlighted the importance of turbulence modeling, employing the standard $\hat{\epsilon}$ - $\hat{\alpha}$ model for robustness and reasonable accuracy across a range of turbulent flows. The research acknowledges several limitations in current computational approaches to hypersonic re-entry analysis. The research relied on standard turbulence models, which may not fully capture the complex physics of hypersonic boundary layer transition and separation phenomena and have a margin of error compared to actual results. [3]

Pershing's (1968) analysis of Gemini re-entry module wind tunnel data provides early insights into hypersonic aerodynamic characteristics, by defining a consistent set of parameters for the Gemini B module, assess the accuracy of ground test facilities, and compare predictions with flight test data. though modern CFD approaches have largely forgone such methods. The studies emphasize the role of Navier-Stokes solvers in capturing complex flow phenomena during re-entry, with particular attention paid to grid generation techniques. [4]

3.

METHODOLOGY

A launch or reentry vehicle's CFD analysis usually consists of the following essential steps: (i) Building the re-entry capsule model with CATIA software; (ii) Importing the geometry into ANSYS Meshing; (iii) Simulating the flow by setting boundary conditions in FLUENT solver at different Mach numbers in both 2D and 3D ; and (iv) Post-processing the results to extract insight into the temperature, pressure, and velocity profiles.

4.

RE-ENTRY VEHICLE BODY DESIGN

The Apollo Command Module represents an achievement in reentry vehicle design, exemplifying the blunt-body configuration that has become the standard for crewed spacecraft atmospheric entry. This configuration, validated through extensive ground testing and eleven successful lunar return missions, demonstrated that blunt-body designs could reliably protect crews from the extreme thermal and mechanical loads encountered during high-speed atmospheric entry, establishing design principles that continue to influence modern reentry vehicle development. From Villodi et al. (2024) the capsule is of truncated cone geometry, with its 60-degree half-angle and blunt heat shield, was engineered to maximize aerodynamic drag while minimizing heat transfer to the crew compartment during the hypersonic reentry.

Fig 1: Diagram of the reentry capsule. The dimensions are $l_1 = 1.9558$ m, $l_2 = 3.4306$ m, $r_0 = 4.6939$ m, $r_1 = 0.2311$ m, and $r_2 = 0.1956$ m. [5]

With overall dimensions of 3.65m in length and a maximum diameter of 3.91m at the heat shield, the Apollo CM's design created a strong bow shock wave that deflected most of the high-temperature plasma flow away from the vehicle's surface. The tapered aft section, transitions from the large-diameter heat shield ($r_0 = 4.6939$ m) to the smaller crew compartment radius ($r_1 = 0.2311$ m), provided optimal area usage while maintaining aerodynamic stability throughout the entry corridor.

5.

S-202 FLIGHT DATA

From Shafeeque (2017), to validate the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis of the Apollo 11 Command Module reentry characteristics, flight data from the Apollo AS-202 mission was utilized as a reference benchmark. The AS-202 flight test, conducted as part of the Apollo program's vehicle qualification phase, provided empirical data for assessing hypersonic flow predictions over the Command Module geometry during atmospheric reentry. Three distinct trajectory points from the AS-202 mission were selected for comparative analysis, representing varying atmospheric conditions and flight regimes. Case 1 corresponds to high-altitude conditions at 70.0 km with a velocity of 7.92 km/s, resulting in a Mach number of 26.2 in an atmosphere ($\rho_\infty = 1.52 \times 10^{-4}$ kg/m³, $T_\infty = 227$ K). Case 2 represents the highest altitude point at 77.2 km with reduced velocity (6.49 km/s, $M = 22.7$) in the rare conditions encountered ($\rho_\infty = 2.45 \times 10^{-5}$ kg/m³, $T_\infty = 203$ K). Case 3 captures lower altitude, higher density conditions at 54.6 km ($V = 5.07$ km/s, $M = 15.6$, $\rho_\infty = 6.16 \times 10^{-4}$ kg/m³, $T_\infty = 262$ K). [1]

Table 1: As-202 Selected Trajectory Points and Freestream Conditions

Velocity V(m/s)	Temperature T(K)	Mach No M	Density ρ_∞ (kg/m ³)	Altitude (km)
7920	227	26.2	1.52×10^{-4}	70.0
6490	203	22.7	2.45×10^{-5}	77.2
5070	262	15.6	6.16×10^{-4}	54.6

Table 2: As-202 Trajectory Points and Freestream Conditions

Time* (s)	Alt. (km)	Re ρ^*	V (km/s)	M	ρ_∞ (kg/m 3)	T $_\infty$ (K)	α	β (deg)
4455	76.8	7.5×10^6	8.24	28.6	$3.38e-5$	205	18.2	2.0
4475	71.3	1.8×10^6	8.15	27.6	$8.79e-5$	217	17.9	2.5
4500	70.0	1.0×10^6	7.92	26.2	$1.52e-4$	227	17.8	2.5
4510	66.0	3.2×10^5	7.80	25.6	$1.60e-4$	230	17.8	2.5
4530	64.9	3.4×10^5	7.53	24.5	$1.84e-4$	234	17.9	2.5
4560	60.0	2.7×10^5	7.07	23.2	$1.93e-4$	231	18.1	2.5
4600	71.6	1.3×10^5	6.74	22.9	$7.19e-5$	215	18.3	2.5
4650	76.2	5.7×10^4	6.56	22.8	$3.24e-5$	206	18.5	2.0
4700	77.2	4.3×10^4	6.49	22.7	$2.45e-5$	203	18.5	2.0
4750	74.5	7.6×10^4	6.39	22.0	$4.50e-5$	210	18.4	2.0
4800	67.3	2.1×10^5	6.21	20.5	$1.37e-4$	210	18.4	2.0
4825	62.9	3.5×10^5	5.97	19.2	$2.81e-4$	209	18.3	2.0
4850	58.2	5.3×10^5	5.62	17.6	$4.14e-4$	252	18.3	2.5
4875	54.6	6.9×10^5	5.07	15.6	$6.16e-4$	262	18.4	2.5
4900	52.4	7.6×10^5	4.53	13.2	$8.00e-4$	268	18.6	2.5

* Seconds after launch.
 † Freestream Reynolds number based on body diameter.

6. COMPUTATIONAL SETUP

6.1. Geometry

6.1.1. 2D Geometry:

The geometry was modeled using CATIA.

Fig 2: Dimensions of the reentry capsule in Catia

Fig 3: 3D Model of capsule in Catia

The capsule geometry was imported in ANSYS DesignModeler as STEP (.stp) file and mapped onto the 2D plane. The circular arc has dimensions of 25 meters, with horizontal of 40 meters and a vertical of 50 meters, with far-field boundaries distant sufficient from the capsule. A Boolean subtract operation was along these lines carried out to erase the capsule (utilized as the instrument body) from the segment space to make a clean 2D boundary around the capsule profile. This strategy advertised a beneficial and physically precise geometry arrangement fitting for ANSYS Familiar high-speed outside stream recreations.

Fig 4: Atmospheric far field with the capsule dimensions

Fig 5: Geometry of two-dimensional model with re-entry capsule

6.1.2. 3D Geometry:

Similar to 2D, the capsule was drafted using CATIA. The capsule geometry was imported into ANSYS DesignModeler as a STEP(.stp) file and positioned at the center of the computational domain. A cubic enclosure with dimensions of 50 meters \times 50 meters \times 50 meters was created to define the far-field boundaries around the capsule geometry.

The cubic domain configuration was selected for several key reasons, it provides uniform boundary conditions in all three spatial directions, ensuring symmetric flow development around the capsule without preferential directional bias; the cubic geometry simplifies mesh generation and maintains consistent cell quality throughout the domain and the 50-meter dimension ensures the far-field boundaries are positioned at sufficient distance (approximately 10-15 capsule diameters) from the capsule surface to minimize boundary condition interference with the near-field flow physics.

Fig 6: Geometry of three-dimensional model with re-entry capsule

6.2. Meshing

6.2.1. 2D Meshing:

The high-quality computational mesh was created to solve high-speed external flow over an in-flight reentry capsule employing ANSYS Fluent. The geometry includes a blunt-nosed reentry capsule placed at the center of a larger domain, representing the ambient atmosphere. Proper resolution of the flow field especially the detached bow shock, stagnation region, and wake zone is vital in hypersonic simulations, which require very fine meshing close to the capsule surface and along the anticipated shock trajectories.

To achieve this, an unstructured, non-uniform mesh was developed, with fine meshing in and about the capsule geometry so that size functions for curvature and proximity accurately represented small features and intricate contours. The outer domain was then meshed with coarse elements to minimize computational cost without sacrificing fidelity in the vicinity of critical regions. Edge sizing with a bias factor of 7 and 700 divisions enabled robust node clustering towards the capsule's heat shield and separation regions. Two inflation layers were implemented for adequate resolution of the near-wall viscous effects and the capture of thermal boundary layer with a smooth transition ratio of 0.272 to enable gradual expansion to the outer domain.

The final mesh contained 88,933 nodes and 88,930 elements, with a global element size of 0.25 m, well balanced for solver performance and simulation accuracy. Quality check showed average orthogonal quality as 0.98042 and minimum value as 0.41985, representing superior mesh structure even in areas of high curvature and gradient. A maximum aspect ratio of 4.135 also testifies to the mesh's ability to sustain accuracy for diverse element sizes and shapes. Such a fine meshing approach is critical in re-entry analysis to predict accurately aerodynamic heating, shock standoff distance, and pressure distribution on the capsule's surface during high Mach number descent.

Fig 7: Meshing of two-dimensional model around re-entry capsule

Fig 8: Meshing of two-dimensional model with domain

6.2.2. 3D Meshing:

Three-dimensional computational mesh was performed to analyze hypersonic external flow. The computational domain consists of a cubic geometry with 50 m dimensions on all sides, with the reentry capsule positioned at the center to provide adequate flow development and boundary separation.

Tetrahedral mesh was employed for geometric flexibility and computational efficiency. This approach enables an adequate representation of the capsule's surface geometry while maintaining refinement in high-gradient regions including the detached bow shock, stagnation point, and wake areas. The tetrahedral framework provides superior handling of complex three-dimensional flow features compared to structured alternatives.

Surface refinement was implemented through face sizing on the capsule geometry with element size of 0.2 m to resolve surface pressure distributions and heat transfer rates. The global element size was set to 1.0 m in the outer domain, balancing computational requirements with solution accuracy in uniform flow regions.

Near-wall resolution was achieved using 15 inflation layers extending from the capsule surface to capture boundary layer and viscous effects. The inflation system used a growth rate of 1.2 with a smooth transition ratio of 0.272, ensuring gradual element size transition while maintaining mesh quality and solver convergence.

The final mesh contains 148,156 nodes and 827,180 tetrahedral elements. Quality metrics show orthogonal quality ranging from 0.20 to 0.99, with aspect ratios between 1.16 and 9.14. These values exhibit good element geometry throughout the domain while accommodating the requirements of the boundary layer inflation system.

Fig 9: Meshing of three-dimensional model around re-entry capsule

Fig 10: Meshing of three-dimensional model with domain

6.3. Boundary Conditions

6.3.1. 2D Boundary Conditions

Table 3: Boundary Conditions for 2D

S. No.	Region	Type
1	Inlet	Pressure far field
2	Re-entry Capsule	Walls
3	Outlet	Pressure Outlet
4	Walls	Walls

6.3.2. 3D Boundary Conditions

Table 4: Boundary Conditions for 3D

S. No.	Region	Type
1	Inlet	Pressure far field
2	Re-entry Capsule	Wall
3	Walls	Pressure far field
4	Outlet	Pressure Outlet

Table 5: Fluid Properties

Fluid	Properties
Air	Density: (as of Ideal gas) Viscosity: Sutherland

For different Mach numbers we change gauge pressure at inlet and temperatures at inlet and outlet and reference values we compute from inlet. Following are temperatures and pressures for different Mach numbers.

Table 6: As-202 Selected Trajectory Points and Freestream Conditions

Mach M	Temperature T(K)	Pressure P(Pa)	Density ρ_{∞} (kg/m ³)
26.2	227	196.4	$1.52 \cdot 10^{-4}$
22.7	203	177.1	$2.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$
15.6	262	61.5	$6.16 \cdot 10^{-4}$

6.4. Solver and turbulence model

Density based solver was used for solution with Spalart Allmaras (1eqn) as turbulence model. This model is made for aircraft flows that follow surfaces and deal with strong pressure differences.

7.

RESULTS & ANALYSIS

Following are the simulation results; and the respective pressure, temperature and velocity profiles in 2D and 3D.

7.1. Verification

7.1.1. 2D Verification

7.1.1.1. At Mach 15.6

This figure showcases the velocity streamlines of a two-dimensional model subjected to hypersonic conditions at Mach 15.6. The fluid flow wraps around the capsule with distinct shock formation ahead of the nose, where the streamlines experience intense deceleration and deflection. The flow separates slightly along the body, indicating the interaction between shock and boundary layer. This visualization offers critical insights into the aerodynamic forces acting on the capsule and sets the stage for pressure and temperature distribution analysis.

Fig 11: Velocity Streamline of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 15.6

In this plot, the pressure field is mapped out under the same flow condition. A strong stagnation zone is visible on the capsule's leading edge, where the pressure peaks due to the abrupt deceleration of high-Mach flow. Behind the shock front, the pressure gradually drops along the body, highlighting the subsonic and supersonic zones. This distribution is pivotal for evaluating structural loads and ensuring thermal protection system adequacy for high-altitude reentry.

Fig 12: Pressure distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 15.6

This figure illustrates the velocity contours around a two-dimensional reentry capsule traveling at Mach 15.6. The bow shock is clearly formed in front of the blunt body, causing a sudden drop in flow velocity across the shock layer. The freestream velocity is deflected and decelerated significantly near the stagnation point, where kinetic energy converts into pressure and thermal energy. This region is vital for assessing drag forces and optimizing the capsule's shape to minimize resistance. Downstream of the stagnation zone, the velocity gradually recovers along the capsule sides, forming a stable supersonic wake structure.

Fig 13: Velocity distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 15.6

This plot reveals the intense thermal loading due to the hypersonic entry environment. The highest temperatures occur near the stagnation point, where compression heating is most severe. As the shock-processed gas flows around the body, thermal diffusion and viscous effects contribute to a gradually declining temperature profile. The separation and reattachment zones, if present, further influence localized heating. Understanding this distribution is crucial for designing the capsule's thermal protection system (TPS) and identifying zones susceptible to ablation or thermal degradation.

Fig 14: Temperature distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 15.6

This figure captures the dramatic pressure gradients experienced by the capsule during reentry at Mach 22.7. The bow shock appears sharply defined, with intense pressure buildup near the stagnation point, visible in the red zone at the nose of the capsule. As the shock wave propagates outward and interacts with the surrounding flow, the pressure tapers off rapidly along the capsule's body, transitioning into lower-pressure regions represented in cooler shades. The zoomed-in view on the right emphasizes localized pressure variations that could influence thermal and structural loads in critical areas. Such data are indispensable for validating aerodynamic design and ensuring safety under extreme high-altitude conditions.

7.1.1.2. At Mach 22.7

Fig 15: Pressure distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

Here, the velocity contours reveal the immense speed gradients encountered at Mach 22.7. Compared to the lower Mach case, this scenario shows a narrower and sharper bow shock, along with a more pronounced velocity gradient near the surface. The increased flow energy heightens the importance of grid resolution near the shock layer. This distribution assists in identifying critical regions for aerodynamic shaping and drag reduction strategies.

Fig 16: Velocity distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

This final plot presents the surface and flowfield temperature variations, highlighting the thermal stress imposed at this extreme Mach number. The nose region endures the maximum thermal load, where kinetic energy converts sharply into internal energy. Downstream, the temperature gradually tapers but remains significantly elevated compared to the ambient. This data is vital for selecting materials with high thermal resistance and for optimizing ablation performance.

Fig 17: Temperature distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

7.1.1.3. At Mach 26.2

This plot illustrates the severe pressure environment encountered at Mach 26.2. A highly compressed region is seen at the stagnation point, where the incoming hypersonic flow confronts the capsule's blunt nose, generating a strong normal shock. The steep pressure gradient in this zone underscores the need for robust structural design to withstand intense aerodynamic loads. The pressure then rapidly diminishes along the body, reflecting the transition into the wake region where pressure recovery occurs.

Fig 18: Pressure distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

This figure displays a distinct velocity field shaped by the extremely high-speed inflow. The bow shock stands extremely close to the body, causing an abrupt velocity drop at the shock layer. The lowest velocities are concentrated at the stagnation region, where kinetic energy is entirely dissipated. As the flow travels along the capsule's surface, velocity gradually recovers, indicating reattachment and streamlined motion downstream. This behavior is crucial in mapping aerodynamic drag and predicting potential flow separation zones.

Fig 19: Velocity distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

Thermal effects are prominently illustrated here, with the highest temperature observed just behind the bow shock near the capsule's leading edge. The intense kinetic-to-thermal energy conversion due to both compression and viscous dissipation results in extreme surface heating. The temperature slowly decreases along the capsule flanks, although it remains elevated, signifying sustained thermal stress. This distribution highlights the importance of advanced thermal protection systems for safeguarding internal components during high-enthalpy reentry.

Fig 20: Temperature distribution of two-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

7.1.2. 3D Verification

7.1.2.1. At Mach 26.2

The pressure distribution analysis reveals critical information about the loading conditions that the spacecraft structure must withstand during re-entry. At the Mach 26.2 condition, representing the higher energy re-entry scenario, the pressure distribution demonstrates extremely high stagnation pressure at the vehicle's leading edge, where the kinetic energy of the hypersonic flow is converted to pressure and thermal energy through the stagnation process. The simulation results show steep pressure gradients across the shock layer, with intense pressure concentration in the stagnation region clearly indicated by the red and yellow contours in the computational results. The radial pressure variation demonstrates maximum values at the centerline of the vehicle, with gradual decrease toward the periphery, creating a characteristic pressure distribution pattern that directly correlates with the expected heat flux distribution on the vehicle surface.

Fig 21: Pressure distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

The velocity distribution analysis provides crucial insights into the flow deceleration characteristics and kinetic energy conversion processes occurring during hypersonic re-entry. At Mach 26.2, the velocity contours reveal dramatic velocity variations across the flow field, with the freestream flow maintaining extremely high velocities represented by the orange and red regions in the computational results, while the region immediately behind the bow shock shows significantly reduced velocities indicated by the blue contours. The triangular wake region behind the vehicle demonstrates near-stagnant flow conditions, creating a complex velocity gradient that extends far downstream of the vehicle. The sharp velocity transition across the bow shock illustrates the intense deceleration that occurs as the hypersonic flow encounters the vehicle, with velocity drops of several kilometers per second occurring across distances of mere centimeters.

Fig 22: Velocity distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

The temperature distribution analysis reveals the extreme thermal environment that spacecraft encounter during hypersonic re-entry, providing essential data for thermal protection system design and materials selection. At Mach 26.2, the temperature contours show peak temperatures occurring in the stagnation region immediately behind the bow shock, where the kinetic energy of the hypersonic flow is converted to thermal energy through viscous dissipation and compression effects. The temperature field exhibits a characteristic pattern with maximum values at the stagnation point, represented by the red and orange regions in the simulation results, followed by a gradual temperature decrease toward the vehicle's periphery and into the wake region.

Fig 23: Temperature distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

7.1.2.1. At Mach 22.7

At the lower Mach 22.7 condition, representing standard orbital re-entry velocities, the pressure distribution exhibits similar patterns but with reduced absolute magnitudes, demonstrating the strong dependence of aerodynamic loading on flight velocity. The analysis shows comparable shock standoff distance and overall flow structure between the two conditions, but with proportionally lower peak

pressures and more moderate pressure gradients. This comparison illustrates how even relatively small changes in re-entry velocity can significantly impact the severity of the aerodynamic environment, which has direct implications for thermal protection system design requirements and structural loading considerations.

Fig 21: Pressure distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

The velocity distribution at Mach 22.7 shows similar qualitative patterns but with proportionally lower absolute velocity magnitudes throughout the flow field. The wake region exhibits comparable stagnation characteristics, but the velocity gradients are less severe due to the reduced incoming flow velocity. The cross-sectional views reveal the three-dimensional nature of the velocity field, showing how the flow accelerates around the vehicle's periphery while maintaining low velocities in the central wake region. This velocity distribution directly influences the pressure recovery in the wake and affects the vehicle's base drag characteristics, which are critical for accurate trajectory prediction and control system design.

Fig 22: Velocity distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

The temperature distribution demonstrates the formation of a high-temperature boundary layer along the vehicle surface, where viscous effects create additional heating through friction and velocity gradients. The wake region shows significantly lower temperatures, indicated by the blue contours, due to the reduced flow velocities and expansion effects in this area. At the lower Mach 22.7 condition, the temperature distribution maintains similar qualitative characteristics but with reduced peak temperatures, demonstrating the strong correlation between flight velocity and thermal loading. The temperature gradients are less severe at the lower Mach number but still represent challenging thermal environments that require careful consideration in thermal protection system design. The three-dimensional temperature distribution reveals the complex thermal environment around the entire vehicle, showing how temperature varies not only in the streamwise

direction but also circumferentially around the vehicle. The cross-sectional views illustrate the thermal boundary layer development and the heat transfer characteristics that determine the thermal loading on different parts of the vehicle structure. This temperature distribution data is essential for predicting material performance, thermal stress development, and the overall thermal protection system requirements throughout the re-entry trajectory

Fig 23: Temperature distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

8.

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

8.1. Validation of CFD results

To validate the present CFD results, a comparison was made with the published data from [1] where external flow around a reentry capsule was simulated under similar conditions. Following results are of published data:

Fig 24: Pressure distribution of two-dimensional model

Fig 25: Velocity distribution of two-dimensional model

Fig 26: Temperature distribution of two-dimensional model

Fig 29: Temperature distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 26.2

Fig 30: Temperature distribution of three-dimensional model at Mach no = 22.7

We focused on three main parameters for validation: the bow shock, stagnation pressure, and the distribution of wall temperature.

First off, the shock stand-off distance in our simulation showed a noticeable upstream curvature that closely resembled the shock structure detailed in the reference study. While we didn't have exact numerical values to compare, the estimated gap between the bow shock and the capsule nose looked quite similar in both scenarios, suggesting a solid agreement. Next, the stagnation point pressure in our simulation created a clear high-pressure core at the capsule's nose, matching both the location and intensity found in the reference results. This indicates that we accurately captured the compressible flow behavior and shock focusing. Lastly, the wall temperature distribution revealed peak heating concentrated around the nose area in the reference study. The thermal gradients along the capsule's surface followed a similar pattern aligning with the post-shock thermal zone. The 3D results generally corroborate the 2D findings while providing additional insight into the three-dimensional flow structure. The agreement between 2D and 3D solutions validates the assumption of axisymmetric flow for this configuration, though the 3D model captures subtle three-dimensional effects that may be important for detailed engineering analysis.

The overall flow behavior, including the shock structure and pressure distribution, closely matched the trends observed in the reference work. This strong agreement confirms the validity of the current simulation setup and numerical approach.

9.

CONCLUSION

A comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis was performed in the current study to study the external high-speed flow field around a reentry capsule. A 2D and 3D domain was modeled in ANSYS Design Modeler in a modular way using the capsule geometry from a STEP file and the surrounding flow region as needed. Mesh Independent studies were performed with fine meshing using Proximity, curvature refinements and two layers inflation to capture the near wall flow. Mesh quality measures such as orthogonal quality and aspect ratio supported the suitability of the mesh for reliable compressible simulation.

The simulation outcomes offered a concise understanding of significant aerodynamic aspects such as bow shock development, pressure characteristics near the stagnation point, while studying the wall temperature. These results were validated against a benchmark study, revealing close alignment in shock stand-off distance, stagnation pressure characteristics, and thermal distribution patterns.

In conclusion, the study illustrates essential flow features for reentry vehicles. This approach can be further applied to parametric studies analyzing variations in angle of attack, Mach number, or shape optimization to enhance the thermal and aerodynamic design of future reentry capsules.

10.

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